

VitaLabs Project Submission Form

Please complete all sections clearly. Each question has specified character or word limits.

Part 1: Project Overview

1. Project Title

Precision medicine for brain health informed by gene-mapped MRI features

2. Short Description

Regional brain aging trajectories vary among individuals. The published literature suggests that inter-individual variability in regional brain aging dynamics can be mapped to gene variants, gene network architectures, and gene expression patterns, which can inform personalized interventions for the maintenance of brain health, as well as the prevention of age-related structural/functional deterioration. To address the hallmarks of brain aging in a personalized manner, our project will develop a multicomponent AI/ML model using cross-sectional and longitudinal brain imaging scans, annotated with person-level genome sequencing data, to infer the optimal intervention targets for specific brain aging signatures. We will restrict our initial use case to white matter microstructural integrity, characterized by diffusion MRI metrics often declining with age, as it is an understudied feature of the aging brain with a critical role in overall inter-regional coordination and executive function across the lifespan.

3. Project Keywords

List 4-5 keywords that summarize the project focus.

- Keyword 1: white matter microstructural integrity
- Keyword 2: magnetic resonance imaging
- Keyword 3: computational genomics
- Keyword 4: artificial intelligence
- Keyword 5: personalized medicine

4. At-a-Glance Questions

Answer these questions to provide an immediate snapshot of the project:

- **What problem does the project address?**

Brain inter-regional coordination, maintained by white matter, is crucial for executive function, processing speed, and cognitive ability. We aim to address age-related white matter integrity loss.

- **Why is the project relevant for longevity science?**

Brain aging is non-uniform, following person-level developmental and context-specific trajectories. We disentangle complex phenomic associations for personalized brain functional longevity.

- **What makes this project innovative or distinctive?**

We work at the intersection of structural, genomic, and pharmacological spaces to achieve brain health, e.g. white matter microstructural integrity, in a personalized fashion.

- **What will be the main outcome of this project?**

An AI/ML-inspired model for deducing personal brain aging trajectories for patient stratification and the identification of potential targets for novel therapeutics.

- **How much funding are you requesting?**

50,000 USD.

Part 2: Detailed Project Description

5. The Problem

Brain aging is a multifaceted process (1). Functional deterioration, e.g. decline in executive function, has its structural counterparts, with different brain regions “aging” at different rates (2). Consequently, ML-aided analysis of volumetric brain imaging data paired with chronological age allowed the creation of **BrainAGE**, an aging clock that can impute biological age from brain scans (3). Although regional grey matter volumes show a consistent reduction from ~50 years onwards (1), for white matter the reported volumetric change is modest (4). A drastic change, however, is seen on a microstructural level, where declining parameters like fractional anisotropy, measured using diffusion-weighted MRI, reflect the age-related loss of white matter integrity (5). Made of axon bundles, where the diffusion of

water normally is highly directional (anisotropic), white matter integrity is crucial for complex tasks, requiring intact brain inter-regional coordination (6). The integrity loss can be attributed to microvascular damage, degeneration of myelin sheaths around axons, decreasing axonal density, etc (5). It has been linked to a decline in executive function in the elderly (7–11), correlated with the level of physical activity (12), and shown to be associated with epigenetic age acceleration (13) and telomere length (14).

6. The Solution

Given the mentioned heterogeneity and crude volumetric measures of total grey/white and regional volumes not fully capturing the underlying dynamics, a more granular approach to assessing brain aging is warranted. Normative models based on large population datasets enable the detection of deviations from an expected normative developmental trajectory, providing insights into individual brain aging characteristics (15, 16). Pinpointing local deviations from the norm is more informative than assigning a single scalar value (e.g., “brain age”) to an individual, with the potential to inform person-level precision interventions if (micro)structural brain aging longitudinal phenotypes are mapped onto genetic data.

To realize this potential, we envision an AI-inspired normative model, that will be trained on e.g. **UK Biobank** brain imaging datasets annotated with genetic data (17, 18), that would identify personal features of brain aging. The revealed phenotype-to-genotype associations, complemented by the gene expression dimension, e.g. **GTEx** (19), will then be used to identify key nodes for therapeutic intervention in a personalized fashion, e.g. for white matter integrity. Further, the model may be useful for patient stratification and drug repurposing; and will enable the rational development of novel drugs informed by genetic, functional, and structural information. The model ultimately provides drug targets and personalized interventions that may alleviate brain deterioration and improve patient outcomes.

Presently, the vision for the model is broad; however, it has an idea of multimodal data integration at its core to deduce not-too-obvious associations for practical application. Should we decide to focus on certain genes/gene products for the global promotion of white matter health or, conversely, for the amelioration of regional or trait-specific processes, our next

steps and the choice of modalities will depend on the actual target suggested by the model. Our considerations are given next.

7. What Makes This Project Distinctive?

White matter integrity is an overlooked feature of the aging brain that cannot readily be inferred from common structural MRI, with diffusion metrics often preceding conspicuous volumetric changes by decades. On the other hand, given the overall importance of white matter for integral brain function throughout the lifespan, measures of neural tract microstructural integrity are an indispensable metric for monitoring optimal brain health. Most efforts for optimizing brain performance and longevity focus on grey matter and/or are informed by population-level averaged approaches, disregarding the brain regional heterogeneity both in terms of personal developmental trajectories and the associated gene polymorphic and expressional backgrounds. With our project, we address the understudied facets of brain aging at the intersection of brain regional peculiarities, temporal dynamics, and genetic context, i.e. offering a solution for patient stratification and personalized therapy for a healthy brain.

8. Expected Impact and Innovation

Our model will be impactful and innovative in two ways: 1. it will trace personal brain aging trajectories with the regional resolution (in other words, both spatially and temporally), mapping them to genomic and transcriptomic profiles, using known genotype-to-phenotype associations, e.g. **ClinVar**, and gene expression signatures from the **GTEX** dataset imputed onto SNP data, – in order to deduce multidimensional brain aging signatures particular to a given individual, or patient; 2. it will feed off of the brain aging signatures to identify targets to modulate underlying phenotypes for personalized interventions in aging and disease. For specific indications, we will use **OMIM** (<https://www.omim.org/>), **DisGeNET** (<https://disgenet.com/>), or **MedGen** (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/medgen/>) to enable drug discovery.

To sum up, deviations of personal trajectories from the normative trajectory, as well as the linked gene variant/gene network architectures, will be useful for patient stratification and the identification of novel targets for achieving maximal therapeutic benefit. We will assess the model in both contexts to decide which route to prioritize. However, our main interest is the intersection

of structural, genetic, and pharmacological domains for patient-level intervention granularity.

Part 3: Funding Request and Budget

9. Requested Funding Amount

Total funding requested for the project (USD): 50,000

10. Milestone-Based Budget and Timeline

Break down the funding request for the duration of VitaLabs (4 months total) into key project milestones. Include descriptions, expected outcomes, duration, and costs.

Milestone	Description	Duration	Cost (USD)
Data: - acquisition - formatting	- Data access to UK Biobank: brain imaging data annotated w/ genetic data; location of published datasets; generation of synthetic data - Gene expression/SNP data retrieval - Compute/storage purchase	1 mo.	13,000
Components: - clean-up - coding - training	- Data cleaning & formatting for model training - Documentation inspection - Coding oversight (for outsourced tasks) - Establishing individual module protocols; basic tests - Normative model training	2 mo.	26,000
MVP: - evaluation - assembly - test runs - debugging	- Initial results evaluation; test predictions generated. - Backend components assembly - Create documentation; assess technical next steps	1 mo.	11,000
Total		4 mo.	\$50,000

11. Long term vision

After we have gotten our working model, the next step would be validation and specialization. Here, subsequent tasks are two-fold: 1. validate how the model measures up against the conventional diagnosis protocols; 2. see if the model is useful for target prediction for the development of novel therapeutics. For the former, we envision validation datasets complemented with electronic health records for the retrospective evaluation of interventions and outcomes, or small trials whereby such evaluations are done in real time. For the latter, the starting point would be targeting the identified intervention hotspots in suitable in vitro model systems for the modulation of underlying phenotypes. For example, **murine spinal cord-derived myelinating cell cultures** (20) and **iPSC-derived myelinoids** (21) to study myelination in the context of white matter integrity, should myelination-associated targets be identified.

For the proof-of-concept validation stage, we will be looking for ~500,000 USD in (pre-seed) funding.

Part 4: Team and Contact Details

12. Lead Researcher Information

- **Full Name:** Rakhan Aimbetov
- **Email:** r@overlake.bio
- **Institution/Organization:** Overlake
- **Position/Role:** R&D lead
- **LinkedIn Profile:** <https://www.linkedin.com/in/raimbetov/>
- **Twitter (if applicable):**

12. Supporting Team Members

List key contributors to the project and their roles.

- **Team Member 1:** Nathan Maton | Data scientist
- **Team Member 2:** -Open slot for a brain imaging expert-

13. Project Website or Additional Resources

If available, provide links to supporting websites or documents relevant to the project.

Project folder -

https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/16-IhztpMfuIvzWalNd0_idMI4LSm_ODM?usp=drive_link

Part 5: Additional Notes and References

14. POI

Root: 0x1c8353c0f3c565f516311c908134193490450f7932792d58beaedc5949f8e760

Txn hash: 0x07b3230935b496857ecfbee8498e6f1ea87d772b11125ec5721420943aed708f

15. Discord thread link

<https://discord.com/channels/810893413880561704/1313253623328800848>

16. Additional Notes

Any additional information or clarification you'd like to provide.

- As an initial concept, the model will get the data on the druggable genome from **Pharos** (<https://pharos.nih.gov/>) and **DrugBank** (<https://go.drugbank.com/>) databases. Technically, this step is drug repurposing with the potential to leverage FDA-approved compounds. Should we decide to go after novel patentable drugs aimed at targets we will have identified during our analyses, services such as **Pharma.AI** (<https://pharma.ai/>) can further be used to have an idea of what the therapeutics could be, taking advantage of the generative AI toolkit for subsequent R&D.

- Secondly, the model can be used for patient stratification for precision medicine tailored to a patient's genetic make-up, e.g. gene SNPs and regional transcriptomic profiles, and a specific condition, informing healthcare providers on the most appropriate intervention for a given deviation from the normative developmental trajectory to achieve a robust and personalized therapeutic outcome. For MVP purposes, we might look for and use existing solutions that we could fork and integrate into our model. After we have gotten a working prototype, we may aim for a proprietary codebase, fitted for the overall model architecture and the biological particulars of R&D tasks.

17. Attachments (if applicable)

A concept model diagram -

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